

PROCEEDINGS BOOK

INTERNATIONAL MEDITERRANEAN CONGRESS

November 16-18, 2022, Mersin, Türkiye

Edited by

Asst. Prof. Dr. Mehmet Emin KALGI

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Proceedings Book

SIMULATION OF IDENTIFICATION SYSTEM TAGS BY RADIO FREQUENCY (RFID) FOR HOSPITAL APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

The Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) system is a technology in which data communication is carried out by means of electromagnetic waves, with the main objective of facilitating information management, thus allowing the traceability and monitoring of data and objects without the need for a material medium. Therefore, the application of this technology has incorporated numerous sectors, including hospital management. The scope of RFID technology in the health area and also in the field of physical fitness tests, directly contribute to the reduction of human errors, often resulting from the difficulty of tracking and continuous monitoring of patients. Therefore, the objective is the study of this technology, especially with regard to hospital purposes, from the computational modeling of RFID tags in the CST Studio Suite software. The choice of this analysis methodology was based on its ability to predict the behavior of the physical phenomena that govern the material and/or the component being evaluated, so the repeated sequencing of an experiment in the computational environment makes possible, as a consequence, the real reproduction of the model of more efficiently, both in terms of functionality and the resources invested in its construction. In this way, evaluating the data resulting from the simulations for models of tags already used today, the possibility of new applications within the hospital context will be verified.

Keywords: Radio frequency, Hospital, Simulation.